

Electrochemical behavior and biological aspects of thio-Schiff bases and their copper complexes

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Abstract : The sulfur-nitrogen donor ligands, thiosemicarbazones of 5-nitro-1*H*-indole-2,3-dione, 6-nitro-1*H*-indole-2,3-dione and 5-chloro-1*H*-indole-2,3-dione have been prepared by the condensation of thiosemicarbazide with respective ketones in 1 : 1 molar ratio in the ethanol medium. Copper complexes were prepared by the reaction of hydrated copper dichloride with an equimolar and bimolar amount of ligands. Newly synthesized complexes have been characterized by elemental analysis, melting point determinations and UV, ESR and IR spectral studies. In all the complexes, the monobasic bidentate nature of the ligand is evident. Probable tetrahedral and square planar structures for the 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes, respectively, have been proposed on the basis of spectral data. Antibacterial and antifungal studies of these compounds against various pathogenic bacterial and fungal strains have been carried out. All the ligands and their metal chelates were found active against all microbial strains investigated. However, the chelates were found to be more active than the ligands. One of the ligands (L³H) and its metal chelate (CuCl(H₂O)L₃) were screened for their antifertility activity. The results indicated that the administration of copper compound in male rats brought about an interference with spermatogenesis which ultimately caused infertility.

Keywords : Thio-Schiff bases, Cu^{II} complexes, synthesis, spectral studies, antifungal, antibacterial and antifertility activity.

Introduction

Schiff bases are an important class of compounds in medicinal and pharmaceutical fields. They show biological applications including antibacterial¹⁻³, antifungal⁴⁻⁸ and antitumor activities^{9,10}. Many of researchers studied the synthesis, characterization and structure-activity relationship (SAR) of Schiff bases¹¹⁻¹⁴. It is reported that salicylaldehyde derivatives, with one or more halo-atoms in the aromatic ring, showed variety of biological activities including antibacterial and antifungal activities¹⁵. Similarly indole derivatives¹⁸ prepared for a long time for a variety of biological activities such as CNS depressant, anticancerous, antibiotic, antihistaminic, anticonvulsants and many others. Schiff base complexes with transition metals have also played a prominent role in the development of coordination chemistry. Several Schiff base metal complexes have been studied because of their industrial and biological applications¹⁶.

The chemistry of isatin and its derivatives is particularly interesting because of their potential application in medicinal chemistry. Surprisingly isatin derivatives show

anti-HIV activity too. Therefore, the research interest on isatins has expended day to day and some important heterocyclic derivatives of isatins and consequent study of their cytotoxicity have been reported¹⁷. Isatin thiosemicarbazone derivatives exhibit interesting applications as research tools in physiological studies¹⁸. Many isatin-derived compounds possess a wide spectrum of medicinal properties and, thus, have been studied for activity against tuberculosis and leprosy, as well as for fungal¹⁹, viral, and bacterial infections²⁰. A survey of the literature reveals that the biological activity of the Schiff base was enhanced by complexation²¹.

The chemistry of thiosemicarbazones has received considerable attention in view of their variable bonding modes, promising biological implications, structural diversity, and ion-sensing ability²²⁻²⁴. They have been used as drugs and are reported to possess a wide variety of biological activities against bacteria, fungi, and certain type of tumors and they are also useful models for bioinorganic processes²⁵. The inhibitory action is attributed due to their chelating properties²⁶⁻³⁶.

The activity of these compounds is strongly dependent upon the nature of the heteroatomic ring and the position of attachment to the ring as well as the form of thiosemicarbazone moiety³⁷. These are studied extensively due to their flexibility, their selectivity and sensitivity towards the central metal atom, structural and similarities with natural biological substances, due to the presence of imine group (-N=CH-) which imparts the biological activity³⁸. Copper(II) complexes of thiosemicarbazones are good antimicrobial agents as reported³⁹. Thomas and Parmeswaran⁴⁰ studied the antitumour activities of copper chelates of anthracene-9-carboxaldehyde thiosemicarbazone and Murthy and Dharmaraja⁴¹ reported the cytotoxic activity of phenylglyoxal bis(thiosemicarbazone) against Ehrlich ascites carcinoma cells in copper complexes.

Metal complexes of some hydrazones, particularly those of Cu^{II} have been reported to show antitumour activity, others are useful in polymer coatings, inks and pigments. A number of copper complexes with various ancillary ligands have also been reported by Turel *et al.*⁴². Copper(I) complexes can be obtained directly from the Cu^{II} compounds by ligand reduction. Considering the constant emergence of antibiotic resistance to clinically used compounds, it is of critical importance to develop novel antibiotic classes, which eventually would target the lipid layer of the organisms and other aspects of the pathogen life cycle. Preparation, spectroscopic investigations, antibacterial, antifungal and antifertility activity results of the newly synthesized ligands and their metal chelates are discussed in this paper.

Experimental

Chemicals :

The hydrated copperdichloride, CuCl₂.2H₂O was purchased from Alfa aesar and used as such. Different isatin derivatives were synthesized by the use of appropriate aniline as described for organic compound synthesis. The procedure used for the synthesis is reported earlier⁴³. Solvents of analytical grade were distilled and dried from appropriate drying agents immediately prior to use.

Physical measurements and analytical methods :

Molecular weights of the newly synthesized ligands and their metal complexes were determined by the Rast

Camphor method. Sulfur and nitrogen were estimated by the Messenger's and Kjeldahl's method, respectively. Copper was estimated volumetrically. ESR spectra of the complexes were monitored on Varian E-4X band spectrometer. The electronic spectra were recorded on a Varian-Cary/5E spectrophotometer at SAIF, IIT, Madras, Chennai. Infrared spectra of the ligands and their complexes were recorded in the region, 4000–200 cm⁻¹ with the help of Nicolet Magna FTIR-550 spectrophotometer on KBr pellets. Voltammetric measurements were performed with a Metrohm Computrace Voltammetric Analyzer μ AUTOLAB TYPE III Potentiostat Ecochemie (Utrecht, The Netherlands) Model 757 VA. A conventional three-electrode system was used consisting of an Ag/AgCl/KCl reference electrode, a hanging mercury drop electrode (HMDE) as a working electrode and a graphite rod as auxiliary electrode. The whole measurements were automated and controlled through the programming capacity of the apparatus. The data were treated through a PC connected to the Electrochemical Analyzer version-757 VA computrace.

Synthesis of thio-Schiff bases :

The ligands, thiosemicarbazones of 5-nitro-1*H*-indole-2,3-dione, 6-nitro-1*H*-indole-2,3-dione and 5-chloro-1*H*-indole-2,3-dione were prepared by the condensation of thiosemicarbazide with respective ketones in 1 : 1 molar ratio in ethanol by the condensation method. Their physico-chemical properties and analytical data are given in Table 1. The parent ligands exist in the tautomeric forms (Fig. 1).

Synthesis of the complexes :

A weighed amount of hydrated copperdichloride reacts with the ligands in unimolar and bimolar ratios, in dry methanol. The reaction mixture was thoroughly shaken and then refluxed for 12 to 14 h on fractionating column. The excess of the solvent was distilled off after the completion of the reaction and the compound was repeatedly washed with *n*-hexane and then followed by drying in vacuum for an hour to get the final purified product. The synthetic data, physical properties and analytical data of the compounds are enlisted in Table 1.

In vitro study :

The purpose of the *in vitro* antimicrobial activity screening program was to provide the antimicrobial activity of the investigated ligands and their metal complexes.

where, X = 5-NO₂ (L¹H), 6-NO₂ (L²H) and 5-Cl (L³H)

Fig. 1. Structure of the ligands.

Table 1. Analytical data and physical properties of the ligands and their complexes

Compd.	Molar ratio	Colour	Melting point (°C)	Found (Calcd.) (%)			Mol. wt. Found (Calcd.)
				N	S	M	
C ₉ H ₇ N ₅ O ₃ S (L ¹ H)	-	Dark brown	247	26.32 (26.40)	12.26 (12.08)	-	249.54 (265.24)
C ₉ H ₇ N ₅ O ₃ S (L ² H)	-	Gray	221	26.16 (26.40)	12.24 (12.08)	-	281.42 (265.41)
C ₉ H ₇ N ₄ O ₃ Cl (L ³ H)	-	Dim yellow	257	22.12 (21.99)	12.54 (12.58)	-	270.17 (254.69)
[CuCl(L ¹).H ₂ O]	1 : 1	Parrot green	175-180	18.36 (18.47)	8.41 (8.52)	16.66 (16.54)	381.25 (405.68)
[Cu(L ¹) ₂]	1 : 2	Parrot green	180-185	2.36 (2.45)	10.83 (10.95)	10.90 (10.78)	592.01 (615.75)
[CuCl(L ²).H ₂ O]	1 : 1	Parrot green	185-190	18.36 (18.47)	8.41 (8.52)	16.66 (16.54)	381.25 (405.68)
[Cu(L ²) ₂]	1 : 2	Parrot green	205-210	2.36 (2.45)	10.83 (10.95)	10.90 (10.78)	592.01 (615.75)
[CuCl(L ³).H ₂ O]	1 : 1	Light brown	183-185	15.76 (15.86)	9.19 (9.05)	17.88 (17.75)	355.29 (341.92)
[Cu(L ³) ₂]	1 : 2	Brown	190-195	20.19 (20.27)	11.56 (11.67)	63.54 (63.45)	518.88 (536.82)

Fungicidal screening :

Potato dextrose agar medium was prepared in flask and sterilized. Accurate amounts of all the compounds were added after being dissolved in methanol so as to get certain final concentrations of 50, 100 and 200 ppm. Aliquots of 15 mL medium were poured in sterilized petriplates. A culture of test fungus is grown on PDA for seven days at the optimum temperature for growth. Small disc of the fungus culture is cut with a sterile cork borer and transferred aseptically in the centre of petridish containing the medium with a certain amount of test compound and incubated for 4 days at 25 ± 2 °C. The colony

diameter was measured after the incubation period of growth. The percentage inhibition of growth was calculated by $(C - T) C^{-1} \times 100$, where C = diameter of the fungal colony in check/control plate, T = diameter of the fungal colony in test plate⁴⁴.

Bactericidal screening :

Flat bottomed petridish were used and nearly 15 mL of the beef extract medium (peptone 5 g, beef extract 5 g, NaCl 5 g, agar-agar 20 g and distilled water 1000 mL) was pipetted out into the petridish. Then bacterial suspension was added and after sometime bacterial growth was seen in the medium. The test compounds were dis-

solved in methanol (tetracyclin was used as standard and methanol as negative control, so methanol do not interfere in zone of inhibition)) to give 500 and 1000 ppm final concentrations. Paper discs of Whatman No. 1 filter paper of 5 mm diameter were soaked in these solutions of varied concentrations. The discs were dried and placed on the medium with organism in petridish at suitable distances. These petridishes were incubated for 24 h at 25 ± 2 °C and zone of inhibition⁴⁵ was measured in mm.

In vivo study :

Antifertility activity :

The healthy Sprague Dawley albino rats (*Rattus norvegicus*) weighing 170–200 g were chosen for experimentation. The animals were housed in clean plastic cages covered with chrome plastic grills at room temperature (20 ± 5 °C) and uniform light (14 : 10 : L : D). The animals were mostly maintained on standard rat feed purchased from Ashirwad Food Industries Ltd., Chandigarh, India and wheat seeds as alternative feed and fresh water *ad libitum*. No rat mortality occurred during the study period. The rats were weighed weekly and changes recorded. The rats were sacrificed after 24 h of the last dose (61st days) to perform various tests. The animals were divided into three groups containing six animals each.

Group-A selected as control and treated with olive oil 0.5 mL/day, which is vehicle chosen to administer the synthesized compounds,

Group-B was treated with ligand (L^3H) 5 mg in 0.5 mL/day olive oil and

Group-C was treated with $CuCl(H_2O)(L_3)$ complex 5 mg in 0.5 mL/day olive oil.

All the compounds were given regularly for 60 days. The mating exposure test was done on day 55th of the experiment.

Fertility test :

On day 56th towards the end of the respective experimental period, each male was housed individually with two proestrous females for 5 days. The females were scheduled for laparotomy 2 weeks later to determine the number and viability of fetuses. After mating, males were removed for autopsy⁴⁶.

Autopsy schedule and body and organ weight measurements :

The animals were weighed and autopsied under light ether anesthesia 24 h after last dose of the treatment.

Blood samples were collected by cardiac puncture in the heparinized tubes for haematological studies. Serum was also separated from non-heparinized clotted blood for the estimation of testosterone level.

Initial and final body weights of the animals were recorded. The animals were dissected and various organs of the reproductive tract viz. testes, epididymis, seminal vesicle, ventral prostate and vas deferens along with liver, kidney, adrenal and heart were excised, cleared of adhering fat and connective tissue and weighed to the nearest mg on a top pan balance.

Body and organ weight measurements :

At the end of experimental period, the animals were weighed and autopsied under light ether anesthesia. The reproductive and accessory sex organs (testes, epididymis, seminal vesicle and ventral prostate) were carefully dissected out, freed from adherent tissues. The weight of each organ was measured with an electronic weighing machine, which has sensitivity of 0.01 g.

Sperm motility and sperm density :

The spermatozoa motility was determined according to the reported method⁴⁷ using a WBC counting Neubauer chamber of a haemocytometer and were expressed as million spermatozoa/mL suspension. The epididymis exposed by a scrotal incision. A cut is made at the distal end of the cauda epididymis and spermatozoa were expressed out by gentle pressure in a fixed amount of physiological saline to make a sperm suspension. Sperm suspension is then placed on a glass slide and observed for forward motility. At least 100 spermatozoa per rat were observed under microscope using pre-calibrated micrometer. The sperm suspension is placed on Neubauer's chamber of haemocytometer and allowed to settle for 1 h. The number of spermatozoa in appropriate squares counted under light microscope at 100 X magnification and then with the help of standard formulae counts/mL were calculated.

Biochemical studies :

Cholesterol was estimated as reported by Zlatkis *et al.*⁴⁸. Glycogen was estimated by the method of Montgomery⁴⁹. The values for the body weight, organ weight, sperm dynamics and biochemical estimations were averaged, standard error of the mean values were calculated and student's 't' test was applied for the standard comparisons.

Electrochemical study :

Stock solution of $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ was prepared in dimethyl formamide (DMF). $1 M$ tetraethyl ammonium perchlorate (TEAP) in DMF was used as supporting electrolyte. All reagents and solvents were of analytical grade (Merck and Sigma).

Voltammetric measurements were performed with a Metrohm Computrace Voltammetric Analyzer μ AUTOLAB TYPE III Potentiostat Ecochemie (Utrecht, The Netherlands) Model 757 VA (Vide : Experimental).

Results and discussion

The unimolar and bimolar reactions of hydrated copper chloride with the monofunctional bidentate $N^{\circ}S$ donor ligands, 5-nitro-3-(indolin-2-one) thiosemicarbazone (L^1H), 6-nitro-3-(indolin-2-one) thiosemicarbazone (L^2H) and 5-chloro-3-(indolin-2-one) thiosemicarbazone (L^3H) can be represented by the following equations :

(where, $N^{\circ}S$ is the donor system of the ligand)

All the reactions are quite facile and led to the formation of the coloured solids. The resulting complexes are insoluble in common organic solvents but soluble in methanol, DMSO, THF and DMF. The molecular weights of these complexes were determined by the Rast Camphor method which indicated their monomeric nature. The non-electrolytic behavior of these complexes in anhydrous DMF is indicated by the low conductance values ($12-16 \Omega^{-1} cm^2 mol^{-1}$) of the molar conductance. The data from analytical and physicochemical studies were correlated to explain the properties and natures of the complexes (Table 1).

Spectroscopic characterization :

Electronic and ESR spectra :

The electronic spectra of the ligands and their Cu^{II}

complexes were recorded in dry methanol. The electronic spectra of the ligands, L^1H , L^2H and L^3H exhibit broad maxima in the range 350–345 nm due to the $n-\pi^*$ electronic transitions of the azomethine group, which undergoes a bathochromic shift in the copper complexes, due to the polarization within the $>C=N$ chromophore caused by the metal-ligand interactions⁵⁰. The electronic spectra of the ligands show two maxima at ~ 275 and ~ 315 nm assigned to $\pi-\pi^*$ electronic transitions within the benzene ring of the ligands. These bands remain almost unchanged in the corresponding metal complexes.

The electron spin resonance spectra of the representative complexes were recorded at room temperature. The 'g' values lie in the range 2.02–2.18 in the present complexes, which are in accordance with the values reported for the tetracoordinated copper complexes.

IR spectra :

A study and comparison of the infrared spectra of the ligands and their metal complexes imply that ligands are bidentate, with the thiolic-sulfur and azomethine-nitrogen as the two coordination sites. The IR spectra of the ligands display sharp bands around $3500-3320 cm^{-1}$ assignable to NH_2 group. These bands remain unchanged in the Cu^{II} complexes, indicating their non-involvement in coordination. Two medium intensity bands in the regions $3240-3230 cm^{-1}$ and $1050-1045 cm^{-1}$ due to $\nu(NH)$ and $\nu(C=S)$ vibrations, respectively, in the ligands disappear in the spectra of the complexes which indicate that complexation takes place through the nitrogen and sulfur atoms. In the ligands, the most significant band in the region $1620-1610 cm^{-1}$ assignable to $\nu(C=N)$ group shifts to the lower frequency in the complexes suggesting the coordination of the azomethine nitrogen to the metal atom. The presence of $\nu(Cu-Cl)$ vibrations at $325-315 cm^{-1}$ is also observed in the 1 : 1 complexes. In the spectra of the 1 : 1 complexes, the coordinated water molecules are identified by a band at $845-688 cm^{-1}$. This is not observed in the corresponding 1 : 2 complexes. The coordination of the azomethine nitrogen and bonding of the thiolic-sulfur to the metal ion is also supported by the appearance of two absorption bands in the regions 405–

385 and 345–332 cm^{-1} in the complexes; which may be assigned to $\nu(\text{Cu}\leftarrow\text{N})$ and $\nu(\text{Cu}\leftarrow\text{S})$ vibrations, respectively. On the basis of the above-mentioned studies, the following possible structures possessing four-coordinated copper nucleus can be proposed for these derivatives (Fig. 2), where, $\text{N}\wedge\text{S}$ is the donor system of the ligand.

1 : 1 Complex

1 : 2 Complex

Fig. 2. Proposed structures of the metal complexes.

Electrochemical study of the synthesized Cu^{II} complexes :

Voltammetric behavior :

The electrochemical behavior of Cu^{II} complex was studied by cyclic voltammetric techniques on HMDE. The cyclic voltammograms of Cu^{II} complex in DMF was recorded at room temperature. The complex show two irreversible peak characteristics for $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}} \rightarrow \text{Cu}^{\text{I}}$ ($E_{\text{p}_c} = -500$ mV) and $\text{Cu}^{\text{I}} \rightarrow \text{Cu}^0$ ($E_{\text{p}_c} = -1100$ mV) reduction. In the anodic direction, the peak at $E_{\text{p}_a} = -700$ mV is assigned to the direct oxidation of $\text{Cu}^0 \rightarrow \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}$. The complex also shows a quasireversible peak for the $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}} \rightarrow \text{Cu}^{\text{III}}$ couple at $E_{\text{p}_a} = +600$ mV with the direct cathodic peak for $\text{Cu}^{\text{III}} \rightarrow \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}$ at $E_{\text{p}_c} = +400$ mV. The peak potential shifted towards more negative values with increase in scan rate, confirming the irreversible nature of the reduction process. The effect of scan rate ($\nu^{1/2}$) on stripping peak current (i_p) was examined under the above experimental conditions. As the sweep rate is increased from 50 to 500 mV/s is at a fixed concentration (3×10^{-3} M) of complex; (i) the peak potential shifted cathodically and (ii) the peak current increased steadily. A straight line is obtained when i_p is plotted against $\nu^{1/2}$.

All these facts pointed towards the diffusion-controlled nature of the electrode process.

The antibacterial studies showed that the ligands and their metal complexes exhibited considerable activity against all the pathogenic bacterial (*Escherichia coli* and *Pseudomonas cepacicola*) and fungal strains (*Alternaria alternata* and *Aspergillus niger*). The complexes are more active than their parent ligands against the same microorganism (Table 2). The higher activity of the metal complexes may be owing to the effect of metal ions on the normal cell membrane. This can be well ascribed to Tweedy's Chelation Theory⁵¹. Changing hydrophilicity and lipophilicity probably leads to bring down the solubility and permeability barriers of cell, which in turn

Table 2. Biological data for the ligands and their metal complexes

Compd.	Antifungal screening (%)					
	Inhibition after 96 h					
	(concn. in ppm)					
	<i>Alternaria alternata</i>			<i>Aspergillus niger</i>		
	50	100	200	50	100	200
L ¹ H	37	45	53	32	40	54
L ² H	33	40	48	34	41	49
L ³ H	38	47	55	33	40	48
[CuCl(L ¹).H ₂ O]	48	56	60	50	56	61
[Cu(L ¹) ₂]	50	60	61	54	62	67
[CuCl(L ²).H ₂ O]	45	55	59	49	54	60
[CuCl(L ²) ₂]	48	58	63	48	53	61
[CuCl(L ³).H ₂ O]	52	58	60	54	59	61
[Cu(L ³) ₂]	56	62	65	56	64	68
Flucanazole	82	100	100	86	100	100

Compd.	Antibacterial screening diameter (mm)			
	of inhibition zone after 24 h			
	(concn. in ppm)			
	<i>Escherichia coli</i>		<i>Pseudomonas cepacicola</i>	
	500	1000	500	1000
L ¹ H	6	7	7	9
L ² H	5	8	6	9
L ³ H	7	9	7	10
[CuCl(L ¹).H ₂ O]	8	10	8	10
[Cu(L ¹) ₂]	9	11	9	12
[CuCl(L ²).H ₂ O]	7	9	7	10
[CuCl(L ²) ₂]	8	10	8	10
[CuCl(L ³).H ₂ O]	8	10	9	11
[Cu(L ³) ₂]	10	12	8	10
Tetracyclin	16	17	15	18

Fig. 3. Cyclic voltammogram of Cu^{II} complex at scan rate 100 mV s⁻¹.

enhances the bioavailability of chemotherapeutics on one hand and potentiality at another. The antimicrobial acti-

vity increases as the concentration increased as more enzymes will become inhibited leading to a quicker death of the organisms, while at lower concentration inhibition is less severe.

Antifertility activity :

Body and organ weights :

No significant change in the body weight was observed throughout the experimental duration in all these groups. On the contrary weights of testes, epididymis, seminal vesicle and ventral prostate were significantly ($P < 0.001$) reduced in Groups B and C compared to the control Group A (Table 3).

Sperm motility and sperm density :

A significant decrease in sperm motility in cauda epididymis⁵² was noticed after treatment with ligands L³H and its copper complexes. Sperm density in testes and epididymides were also reduced after various treatments. The sperm of Groups B and C found sluggishly motile without forward progression compared to the control Group A. The results are summarized in Table 4.

Table 3. Changes in the body weight and weights of reproductive organs after treatment with the ligand (L³H) and its copper complexes

Treatment	Body weight (g)		Organ weight (mg/100 g body weight)			
	Initial	Final	Testes	Epididymis	Seminal vesicle	Ventral prostate
Group-A Control (Vehicle treated) 0.5 ml Olive oil/kg.b.wt./day for 60 days	190 ± 10	200 ± 9	1250 ± 80	495 ± 30	380 ± 35	255 ± 20
Group-B Ligand (L ³ H) 5 mg in 0.5 ml Olive oil/kg.b.wt./day for 60 days	185 ^c ± 7	195 ^c ± 3	1020 ± 70 ^a	359 ± 40 ^a	290 ± 25 ^a	180 ± 10 ^a
Group-C [CuCl(H ₂ O)L ³] 5 mg in 0.5 ml Olive oil/kg.b.wt./day for 60 days (Mean ± SEM of 6 animals)	170 ^c ± 12	182 ^c ± 8	750 ± 43 ^b	195 ± 20 ^b	178 ± 21 ^b	105 ± 10 ^b

a = $P \leq 0.01$ = Significant.

b = $P \leq 0.001$ = Highly significant.

c = $P \leq$ Non significant.

Both the Groups (B and C) compared with control.

Table 4. Effects of the ligand (L^3H) and its copper complexes on sperm dynamics and fertility of male rats

Treatment	Sperm motility (%) (Cauda epididymis)	Sperm density (million/ml)		Fertility (%)
		Testes	Cauda epididymis	
Group-A Control (Vehicle treated) 0.5 ml Olive oil/kg.b.wt./day for 60 days	78 ± 5.0	3.9 ± 0.7	59 ± 5	100% positive
Group-B Ligand (L^3H) 5 mg in 0.5 ml Olive oil/kg.b.wt./day for 60 days	62 ± 3.9 ^a	2.3 ± 0.5 ^a	49 ± 3 ^a	60% negative
Group-C [CuC(H ₂ O)L ³] 5 mg in 0.5 ml Olive oil/kg.b.wt./day for 60 days	42 ± 3.1 ^b	1.1 ± 0.2 ^b	20 ± 2 ^b	85% negative

All figures are ±SEM (n=6)
a = P ≤ 0.01 = Significant.
b = P ≤ 0.001 = Highly significant.
c = P ≤ Non significant.
Groups B and C compared with Group A.

Biochemical changes :

A highly significant decrease ($P < 0.001$) was observed in the glycogen level of the testes in Groups B and C with respect to the control (Table 5). A marked reduction ($P \leq 0.01$ to $P \leq 0.001$) in the protein and sialic acid contents of testes, epididymis, seminal vesicle and ventral prostate were observed after treatment with the ligand and its copper complex. However, testicular cholesterol content was increased significantly ($P \leq 0.01$ to $P \leq 0.001$). Further, a marked reduction in the serum testosterone level was observed after treatment with the ligand and its copper complex⁵³.

Tissue biochemistry :**Protein :**

The protein concentration of the reproductive organs viz. testes, cauda epididymis, seminal vesicle and ventral prostate declined significantly ($P \leq 0.001$) in all the treatment groups (Table 5).

Sialic acid :

The content of sialic acid in the reproductive tissues of male rats i.e. testes, cauda epididymis, seminal vesicle

and ventral prostate showed a significant ($P \leq 0.001$) decline in the treatment groups (Table 5).

Glycogen :

The glycogen content of testes and liver was reduced significantly ($P \leq 0.001$) in all the treatment groups (Table 5).

Cholesterol :

The cholesterol content of testes and adrenal increased significantly ($P \leq 0.001$) in all the treatment groups (Table 5).

Conclusion :

Based on various physicochemical and structural investigations, it was concluded that the ligands act as bidentate ligands forming square planar complexes with Cu^{II} ions. Furthermore, the current study strongly demonstrates that the copper complexes are more effective antimicrobial and antifertility agents than the parent ligands. Voltammetric behavior of Cu^{II} complexes clearly indicated the diffusion-controlled nature of the electrode process.

Table 5. Effect of the ligand (L^3H) and its copper complexes on biochemical parameters of male rats

Treatment	Protein (mg/g)			Sialic acid (mg/g)			Testicular		Serum testosterone (mg/ml)
	Testes	Epididymis	Seminal vesicle	Testes	Epididymis	Seminal vesicle	glycogen (mg/g)	cholesterol (mg/g)	
Group-A	20 ± 8	250 ± 9	240 ± 9	8.57 ± 0.9	7.9 ± 0.7	7.6 ± 0.6	2.7 ± 0.2	8.7 ± 0.6	2.70 ± 0.6
Control (Vehicle treated)									
0.5 ml Olive oil/kg.b.wt./day for 60 days									
Group-B	150 ± 7 ^a	205 ± 7 ^a	180 ± 7 ^a	6.5 ± 0.7 ^a	6.2 ± 0.4 ^a	5.9 ± 0.3 ^a	1.9 ± 0.2 ^a	10.2 ± 0.7 ^a	1.9 ± 0.3 ^a
Ligand (L^3H)									
5 mg in 0.5 ml Olive oil/kg.b.wt./day for 60 days									
Group-C	100 ± 6 ^b	117 ± 6 ^b	120 ± 4 ^b	3.2 ± 0.3 ^b	3.1 ± 0.4 ^b	3.9 ± 0.3 ^a	0.9 ± 0.1 ^b	13.2 ± 0.3 ^b	0.8 ± 0.1 ^b
[Cu(H_2O) L^3]									
5 mg in 0.5 ml Olive oil/kg.b.wt./day for 60 days									

All figures are ±SEM (n=6)
 $a = P \leq 0.01 =$ Significant.
 $b = P \leq 0.001 =$ Highly significant.
 $c = P \leq$ Non significant.
 Groups B and C compared with Group A.

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